

KHOREZM REGIONAL WATER RESOURCES

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Annotation.

This article provides information about the provision of Water Resources of the Khorezm region, the available water resources in the region, as well as measures for their rational use.

Keywords.

Oasis, desert, zhkash, canal, amudarya, agriculture,

Introduction: the province is located in the berk basin, like other regions of Central Asia, and its sharply continental climatic conditions strongly affect the emergence, reproduction and distribution of groundwater and surface water throughout the territory.

The largest and only water source in the province is Amudarya. Amudario has its own influence on the regime of not only the province, but all the waters in the province. This river determines the level of development of the Republican folk-agricultural complex.

Main part: the main inland waters in the territory of the province can be shown Amudaryo, lakes, groundwater and a large number of canals and ditches. The main inland water of the municipality is the Amudary, which flows through its eastern part.

The amudarya is the largest river in all of Turkestan. The territory of the region is made up of sand clay and other deposits brought by Amudarya. The fact that the slope of the place where the amudarya flows is not large, and the location of the river's water-flowing core at almost the same altitude as the level of the plain, also influenced the features of the location of the groundwater of the region. The part of the amudarya that flows through the territory of the region reaches a length of 250 kilometers. 90% of the territory of Uzbekistan is located in the amudarya Basin.

Until the construction of the Amudarya Tuyamoyin reservoir, and 25-30 years ago, there was a lot of water. He changed his posture frequently and was strongly eating his wings. There have been strong annual "dipping" incidents on the river. The river meandered a few hundred yards to the right and to the left. While in the past there was an increase in water in spring and summer, sometimes in winter, due to the phenomena of ice congestion, the level of Amudarya rose by 3-5 meters. At such times, the kayirs were flooded. Even the settlement houses on the river banks were previously encountered in winter cases of freezing.

"Khwarazm is the country where Jayhun can get all his profits," Istahriy said. Amudarya begins with the Vrevsky glacier on the Northern Slopes of Hindikush at an altitude of almost 4950 meters with the name Vakhjir, called Vakhondarya until the place where the Tenga Pomir or Pomirdarya came and joined. The pomirdarya is the second tributary of the Amudarya, which flows out of The Hand of a mountain called Zarkul. From the confluence of the pomirdarya stream to the confluence of the Vakhsh tributary, it exists as Amudarya Panj. The Panj is formed by the confluence of five major tributaries, the Wahondarya, Pomirdarya, the Guit, the Bartongdarya and the Vakhsh rivers.

All tributaries of the Panj start from glaciers and lakes such as wahan, Shughnon, Alichur, Darwaz. Amudaryo flows between high snowy and Rocky Mountains, and the slope drops by 5 meters every kilometer. For this reason, it flows very excruciatingly scary and brings with it a huge amount of mineral rocks in a fuzzy way.

After adding a large tributary Vakhsh to the Panj, it takes the name Amudarya. Then he will be joined by the rivers of Kafirnikhon, Surkhan, and Qunduzdarya.

After Surkhandarya, 1,257 kilometers of masaofa do not add any tributaries to the amudarya and flow through the sands. The river formed the Khorezm Delta due to the large amount of mudflats in the millennia process. It starts with delta Camelina. It is surrounded by Karakum, Qizilqum to the West and East, Ustyurt to the Northwest, and the Aral Sea to the North. Berunius was also interested in the history of the formation of the khwarezmian Oasis. He has suggested that the current Karakum desert site may have been a former occupation. His view of this is dearly true to the outcome of the current investigations. The amudarya expands after the Valley of the camel. This made it possible to issue many channels. The amudarya Delta is the oldest delta up to the narrow gorge (Humorock).

It is mainly home to the Khorezm region. The middle part of the Delta includes the range from Jumortog to Taxiatosh. The most recent Delta includes

areas from Taxiatosh to the insular sea. The lower delta of amudarya (splits into deltas such as Sarikamish, Aqchadarya, Island oldi).

In the lower part of amudarya, it is divided into several branches, such as Aqchadarya, Konnadarya, Daryolik, Erkindarya, Kazakhdarya, Koksuv, Oqdarya, Kipchokdarya, engineer-Ozak. The name amudarya was used 2.5 thousand years ago with different terms. Its earliest name was O'huz. It refers to the Turkic name tilde water. Later Greeks called the word Oxus Oxus, Oxus, Ukes.

In the Middle Ages, the Arabs called him Jayhun. At some point, Waxrud was also referred to as Waxshu. At the same time, parts of the river were also called River, Fish River, Termez River, Kalif River, Urganch River, Khorezm River, Jurjonia River, Omul River. The so-called Amudarya of the river is associated with the name of a fortress called Amuya, which is located on the site of the modern city of Chorjoy, which until the 15th century was one of the major trading centers of Central Asia. Amuya castle was the main and most numerous crossing point between Khuroson and Movaraunahr. It must be because of the fact that at first the river was called the Amuyaq river, there are those who assume that it was later called the Amudarya.

25-30 years ago, there were strong floods in Amudarya. The width of the river bed is 3-5 kilometers from brogan. At flood times, the water horizon is raised to 0.5-1.5 meters relative to the ground. The people built high Damas on both banks of the river in order to avoid flooding. These dambas still survive today. The Damas kept the oasis of Khwarazm from flooding. The terrible "Degish" inflicted great casualties on the people. For example: Degish completely washed and destroyed the city of Kot, the capital of Khorezm, thousands of years ago. After a thousand years, such a partition will fall on the head of the city of Fourkol.

In the amudarya water regime, its Basin plays a large role. In the Pamir-Oloy mountain systems, the catchment area of the river is 200,000 sq.it reaches kilometers. The average elevation of these mountains is 5,000-5,500 meters. Some mountains also reach 6,000-7,000 meters.

Thanks to this, thick and perennial glaciers that do not melt on these lands all year round are fertile. The number of such glaciers exceeds a thousand. The largest of the glaciers is 3 km wide and 71 km long. the coming is Fedchenko glacier. Thanks to this, too, its upper part is saturated with Panj, Vakhsh, blueberries and other rivers, ice, snow water.

Tributaries such as lower-starting Beaver, Kofirnikhon, Kyzylsuv, Surkhandarya, Sherobodarya are saturated with snow-ice waters.

So it turns out that Amudarya is not the same in water mode.

In total, 79 per year in the amudarya Basin kub.km water is collected. In the 1960s, the average amudario was 63 from Karki kub.km., 46 cubes from near the city of Nukus. Km. the water flowed.

As amudarya is a full-fledged River from snow and ice water, its water increases mainly in spring. The maximum water consumption is until may. Nowadays, the phenomena of flooding, "dipping" are almost lost. This was due to the increase in irrigated areas in the amudarya Basin, the construction of dozens of canals, such as Karakum, Amu-Bukhara, which receive water from the river, the construction of the Tuyamoyin reservoir. 4 seasons can be distinguished for Amudaryo.

1.The melting period of seasonal snow reserves (July-September) refers to this as "hydrolytic spring".

2. The consumable summer period of perennial ice (July-September).

3. Autumn Period (September-November).

4. Winter period (December-February).

The first and second season is called the water reproduction period, while the third and fourth season is called the water reduction or mejel period.

During the overflow period, 70-80% of the annual water consumption flows. In amudarya, the mejel period lasts around 200 days on average. The amudaryo quayar section freezes annually. Ice thickness increases as the island brogan. In 1967, in the lower part of Amudarya, the ice thickness reaches 30-45 centimeters.

In terms of the turbidity of the amudarya water, the rivers of Central Asia, are the front in it. The beds that the river brings are very fertile. It contains minerals such as calcium, potassium, phosphorus, nitrogen. It is fertile from other rivers of the world. In the following years, the amount of salts in Amudaryo water greatly increased. This is due to the fact that in the regions of Kashkadarya, Bukhara, Navoi, Khwarazm, the Land Branch is washed away (polluted waters) and thrown back into the river. The increase in Dirty Water leads to a violation of the composition of the soil in the river basin, completely unsuitable for drinking potatoes. In the Khorezm region, a number of channels are released that receive water from the Amudarya, these channels can be divided into 3 systems.

1.Interstate and intra-State Highway channels are rock, Saberniyozboy, Shovot, Gooseberry, Mangitarna, Khongaarna.

2. Inter-farm canals are Pitnak arna, Urganch arna.

3. Canal, Yops and ditches inside the farm.

It is known that historical monuments, monuments in the Khorezm Oasis were directly associated with irrigation structures, canals. The thousandth BC

makes it possible to combine the provincial Arnas with the old irrigation systems. The length of the toshsoka main canal is 175 km. being capable of supplying water to more than 50 flanks. In connection with the construction of the tuyamogin reservoir, the importance of The Rock Canal increased even more and became the largest irrigation system in South Khorezm. As a result, Khorezm made it possible to improve the reclamation of the Toshhovuz regions.

The rock, Swordniyozboy, October arna Urganch arna, Pitnak arna, Soviet and other canals were combined into a single Southern Khwarezm irrigation system. In the south-east of the Khorezm region, a Tuyamoyin reservoir was built. Near the village of Pitnak, the Amudarya flows between the hard rocks and forms the pitnak elbow. In particular, it is in this place that the camel gets its name.

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